

Extraction and separation studies of rhodium(III) with 4-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol in hydrochloric acid medium

K. N. Vidhate, M. K. Lande and B. R. Arbad*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : abr_chem@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 1 November 2007, revised 12 February 2008, accepted 13 February 2008

Abstract : A novel method is proposed for the extraction of microgram level concentration of rhodium(III) from hydrochloric acid medium with 4-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (MBIMTT) dissolved in chloroform as an extractant. It was stripped from organic phase with 1 *M* hydrochloric acid and estimated spectrophotometrically with stannous chloride. The effect of acid concentration and various foreign ions has been investigated. The method is applicable to the analysis of synthetic mixtures. The method is highly selective, simple and reproducible.

Keywords : Rhodium, MBIMTT, solvent extraction.

Introduction

Sulphur containing ligands showed promising effects in the field of analytical chemistry for the separation and determination of platinum metals¹. The electronegativity also plays an important role in the stability of the complexes containing sulphur as donor atoms, the transition metals tending to form covalent bonds. 4-(4-Methoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (MBIMTT) is a sulphur containing ligand and it is highly water repellent. It does not form emulsion at the time of extraction. Because of the determination of small amounts of noble metals in minerals containing large amount of base metals is difficult, the effectiveness of MBIMTT has been evaluated as an extractant for rhodium(III) from variety of rhodium bearing materials and process solutions. The important features of this method are that, it permits selective separation of rhodium(III) from other platinum group metals and base metals which is generally associated with it. It is free from interference from large number foreign ions, low reagent concentration is required and time needed for equilibration is very short for MBIMTT, about 30 s. We report here the use of MBIMTT as an extractant for rhodium(III) from hydrochloric acid medium.

Results and discussion

The extraction of rhodium(III) was carried out from different acid media with 0.1 *M* MBIMTT in chloroform

keeping the aq : org ratio 2.5 : 1. The extraction was found to be quantitative from 1 *M* to 8 *M* hydrochloric acid. The extraction was found to be quantitative in very high concentration of nitric acid but was incomplete in sulphuric acid. Hence the use of 1 *M* hydrochloric acid is recommended for further studies.

Fig. 1. Structure of 4-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

Rhodium(III) was extracted in the presence of different diverse ions (Table 1). The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ions cause $\pm 2\%$ error in recovery of rhodium. The results showed that in the extraction and determination $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the rhodium, these ions did not interfere at the level tested. The reproducibility of rhodium extraction investigated from six replicate measurement was found to be $99.00 \pm 0.95\%$.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures : The separation of rhodium(III) from the platinum group metals and other metals is very difficult. A solution containing $100 \mu\text{g}$ of

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions on the extractive determination of Rh^{III}

Foreign ion	Added as	Amount tolerated (mg)	Foreign ion	Added as	Amount tolerated (mg)
Mn ^{II}	MnCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	15	Mg ^{II}	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	20
Fe ^{II}	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	15	Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	5
Fe ^{III}	FeCl ₃	20	Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	5
U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	5	Ni ^{II}	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5
Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .5H ₂ O	20	Co ^{II}	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	15
Ce ^{III}	CeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O	20	Sn ^{II}	SnCl ₂	5
Zn ^{II}	ZnCl ₂	5	Be ^{II}	BeSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	20
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂	20	Ba ^{II}	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	20
Mo ^{VI}	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .24H ₂ O	5	Cu ^{IIa}	CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	5
Pt ^{II}	PtCl ₂	0.5	Ru ^{III}	RuCl ₃ .xH ₂ O	0.5
Au ^{III}	HAuCl ₄ .4H ₂ O	1	Pt ^{IV}	H ₂ PtCl ₆	1
V ^V	NH ₄ VO ₃ .H ₂ O	5	Cd ^{II}	CdCl ₂ .1/2H ₂ O	5
Sb ^{III}	Sb ₂ O ₃	5	Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	10
Fluoride	NaF	200	Oxalate	(COOH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	200
EDTA	EDTA (disodium salt)	100	Acetate	CH ₃ COONa	100
Iodide	KI	100	Bromide	KBr	100

Rh^{III} = 100 µg; aqueous phase = 1 M HCl; Aq/Org = 25 : 10; extractant = 0.1 M MBIMTT in chloroform.

^aMask with 100 mg of EDTA.

Table 2. Analysis of synthetic mixture

Amount of metal ion (µg)	Rhodium Found (µg)	Recovery ^a (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)
Rh (100) + Au (500)	99.6	99.8	0.05
Rh (100) + Pt (500)	99.4	99.7	0.07
Rh (100) + Ru (200)	99.6	99.8	0.05
Rh (100) + Pd (200)	99.2	99.6	0.06
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Ru (200)	99.2	99.6	0.07
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Pd (200)	99.4	99.7	0.07
Rh (100) + Au (500) + Ru (200)	99.6	99.8	0.05
Rh (100) + Au (500) + Pd (200)	99.8	99.9	0.07
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500)	99.6	99.8	0.05
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Au (200) + Pd (200)	99.4	99.3	0.07
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500) + Fe (2000) + Co (2000)	99.4	99.6	0.07
Rh (100) + Pt (500) + Au (500) + Pd (200) + Fe (2000) + Co (2000)	99.2	99.6	0.06

^aAverage of six determination.

rhodium(III) was taken and known amount of other metals were added. Under the optimum extraction conditions of rhodium(III), there is a quantitative extraction of Au^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Pd^{II}. But the co-extracted metal ions cannot be back-stripped by 1 M hydrochloric acid solution. Thus, the reagent (MBIMTT) is made selective towards rhodium(III) by taking an advantage of the stripant used.

The proposed method allows the separation and determination of rhodium(III) from many metal ions and the results of analysis are shown in the Table 2.

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (MBIMTT) :

The 0.02 mole of 3-n ethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole² and 0.02 mole of anisaldehyde in 50 ml alcohol containing 3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 3–4 h. The product obtained was separated and recrystallized from hot ethanol. A faint yellow coloured needles were obtained (m.p. 170 °C). The structure of MBIMTT is shown in Fig. 1.

PMR spectra of MBIMTT in CDCl₃ showed δ values 2.12 (3H, s, -CH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 8.11 (2H, s, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 8.4 (1H, s, -CH), 3.08 (1H, s, -SH). In the IR spectra of MBIMTT, the bands at 2841 cm⁻¹ has been assigned for CH. The peak at 1608.5 cm⁻¹ is for C=N and for C=S group, there is peak at 779.2 cm⁻¹.

A Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (UV-1601) with 1 cm quartz cells was used for measurement. pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter model LI-120 (± 0.01). A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of rhodium chloride hydrate in dilute AnalaR hydrochloric acid (1 *M*) diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and standardized gravimetrically³. A working solution of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared from it by diluting the stock solution with distilled water. MBIMTT (0.1 *M*) solution was prepared in chloroform. Other standard solutions of different metal ions used to study the effect of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of respective salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid. Solutions of anions were prepared by dissolving the respective alkali metal salts in distilled water. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled de-ionised water was invariably used throughout the measurements.

An aqueous solution containing 100 μg of rhodium(III) and enough hydrochloric acid and water were added to give final concentration of 1 *M* with respect to hydrochloric acid in a total volume of 25 ml. The resulting

solution was transferred to 125 ml separating funnel. The aqueous phase was equilibrated once with 10 ml of 0.1 *M* MBIMTT solution in chloroform for 30 s. The phase was allowed to separate and the metal from the organic phase was stripped with two 10 ml portions of 1 *M* hydrochloric acid. The extract was evaporated to moist dryness in order to remove excess of hydrochloric acid. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of 1 *M* hydrochloric acid and transferred into 50 ml volumetric flask. 10 ml of 20% potassium iodide solution was added and the resultant solution as mixed well and heated for about 15 min in boiling water bath. To the cooled solution, 10 ml of 10% stannous chloride solution was added and diluted up to the mark with distilled water containing 1 *M* hydrochloric acid in final concentration. The un-stoppered flask was placed in the boiling water bath for two minutes. The solution was cooled and the absorbance of the reddish brown solution was measured at 460 nm against a reagent blank. The concentration of rhodium(III) was computed from the calibration curve.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad for providing necessary facilities.

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